

Campus Europae Concept (December 2002)

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Executive Summary: Campus Europae and its contribution to the development of European universities

Campus Europae is the practical realization of the Bologna Process. It strives to combine scientific qualification with international employability and an awareness of a European identity.

The Campus Europae project continues the strong European tradition of the freedom of science. In the areas of research, teaching and learning, the project aims to use the regional particularities which were once of importance for the shared history of Europe, for the common present and future interests of Europe. Furthermore, Campus Europae aspires to contribute to the efforts to overcome national interests and to blend them into a broadly common or unified theme which will be of greater benefit to all.

Campus Europae takes up the suggestions made in Bologna, Salamanca and Prague, and aims to implement them quickly within the "European Higher Education Area" by taking the experiences of previous exchange programmes into account and giving them new impulses:

1. The Campus Europae project adds a European dimension to higher education by providing students with an in-depth knowledge of at least three different European regions (during BA plus MA study programmes).
2. The project will enable students to experience the "European Higher Education Area" initially during BA-programmes – i.e. during the first study phase. This will ensure that those students who will enter professional life – temporarily or permanently – upon graduating with a BA degree can also acquire "European competence".
3. The Campus Europae project demonstrates the European idea of "unity in diversity" by bringing students in contact with the so-called "minor" European countries and languages.
4. The Campus Europae study programme will enable students graduating with a BA degree to communicate in at least three European languages (two for English native speakers). Students graduating with an MA degree should be able to communicate in at least four (respectively three) European languages.
5. Using a new concept of academic exchange, Campus Europae encourages participating universities to improve the quality of their teaching and the transparency of their programmes and courses.

6. Campus Europae increases the international competitiveness and attractiveness of the participating universities.
7. Campus Europae will show the possibility of diversification within study programmes and their mutual recognition without implementing rigid standardization measures.
8. The large number of incoming students will lead to internationalisation: changes in lifestyle and learning culture at the respective universities.
9. Campus Europae adds a European dimension to university degrees and improves employment prospects for graduates in Europe and world wide.

Campus Europae accepts the legal structures presently existing in relation to its participant universities. Therefore, participation is open to any European university, and there are no barriers to entry other than acceptance of the Charter of the European University Foundation.

What is new is inter-university co-operation on four fronts:

- a. the emphasis on the European idea and the objective of promoting a European identity,
- b. the promotion of an early period of study abroad,
- c. the way it addresses linguistic issues,
- d. the use of a standardised procedure for the accreditation of studies.

Particularly, the new approach to linguistic issues (see c. above) will give smaller European countries the chance to attract students from other EU countries.

There are no evident reasons why the Campus Europae concept cannot be applied to other universities or university consortiums not already included under its aegis. The provisions of Campus Europae serve to use Europe's cultural diversity as a competitive advantage and to prepare European students for a future in the global marketplace and within multicultural environments.

1. Objective

The core objective of the Campus Europae project is to enable future university undergraduates to experience the unique quality of a Europe whose major achievements include the Declaration of Human Rights and scientific universalism. Additionally, the project hopes to foster the notion of "unity in diversity" and make students aware of a European identity. The project will create opportunities to develop a comprehensive understanding of learning and working cultures in European regions, which in turn will enable graduates to use and pass on this knowledge in a post-university and post-graduate working context.

Previous university programmes only envisaged that a small minority (5 – 10%) of students (for instance future teachers, physicians, civil servants, economists or engineers) would spend between 3 and 12 months abroad. In contrast, the aim of Campus Europae is to gradually ensure that all students – at least those at universities participating in the Campus Europae project – will complete their courses of study after having spent time away from their "home university". During their three to five years in a BA/MA-programme, students will spend one year each at two universities in two other European countries where different languages are spoken. The first year abroad is to be spent during the BA programme, i.e. the first study phase.

The Campus Europae project continues the strong European tradition of the freedom of science. In the areas of research, teaching and learning, the project aims to use the regional particularities which were once of importance for the shared history of Europe, for the common present and future interests of Europe. Furthermore, Campus Europae aspires to contribute to the efforts to overcome national interests and to blend them into a broadly common or unified theme which will be of greater benefit to all.

The objective of promoting a European citizen/citoyenne is of equal importance as the strictly professional one of mobility. This can be summarised as follows:

- Students from countries whose universities are unable to keep up with international quality standards choose to study in a country where these standards are fulfilled.
- A frequent reason for mobility, especially in the advanced stages of a course of study, is to learn about the latest developments at a university where new breakthroughs appear to be imminent, where appealing "schools of thought" exist or where exceptionally rare specialisations are offered.

- For many disciplines and fields, learning about other regions is an important or even indispensable part of the qualification. This is particularly applicable for linguistics, region-related cultural and social studies, geography, geology and several other subjects.
- A particular reason for studying abroad is the acquisition of skills which will allow the individual to live and work in other countries.

The Campus Europae initiative addresses these characteristics, and supplements them with the "European dimension" by promoting among its students and scholars a comprehension of Europe as a diverse social and cultural unit with the focus placed on the development of a European citizen.

In order to acquire this comprehension, a prolonged stay in the host country(ies) is necessary. The project therefore envisages two one-year periods of residence abroad. The participation of not only a small minority is required, but of as many "normal" students as possible in order to achieve a far-reaching effect in European societies. The project also aims to improve student counseling and to increase the capabilities and potential of students and teachers by creating technical, linguistic and organisational conditions which will ensure that the stipulated requirements are met by all students at participating universities.

Even if the intended objective is not directly and simultaneously achieved in all subject areas, it is essential to the planning process that this aim be pursued subsequently. The quantitative dimensions, which must be changed considerably in relation to previous exchange programmes, require a fundamentally different approach with respect to subject matters, organisational issues, and the promotion of language proficiency.

The large number of exchange students acquired through the project will also have a considerable effect on the universities themselves. Up to 40% of their students could be exchange students, so universities themselves will be "internationalised". Such a unique diversity will also make participating universities attractive to students from non-European countries.

The project relates especially to the reform process for the higher education system in Europe, which was initiated in Bologna in 1999 and continued in Salamanca and Prague in

2001. Without this reform and the context it has created, which has progressed significantly in recent years, the objective of which is the attainment of two degrees (BA and MA) in five years, the Campus Europae project would have been considerably impeded, if, indeed, not rendered impossible. Equally important to the success of the project is the gradually changing manner in which periods spent at European universities have been accredited since the introduction of ECTS (European Credit Transfer System).

However, in order to offer courses within the planned Campus Europae network of universities as quickly as possible, it is necessary to make changes in further areas:

- Firstly, the acceptance and acquisition of several foreign languages must be promoted, in particular with regard to "minor" European languages. Only in this way can the integration of all European nations and regions be possible, irrespective of their size and current economic strength.
- Secondly, the mutual recognition of academic degree programmes must be standardised, in order to accommodate a larger numbers of students. This change is necessary so that courses and degree qualifications can be co-ordinated to allow an exchange process between several universities not only from a technical or organisational viewpoint, but also from a time perspective.
- Thirdly, part of the project includes examining each university's legal, organisational and financial circumstances which will govern the exchange programme to be undertaken by the number of students involved in Campus Europae.

2. The European Higher Education Area

After predominantly US and Australian universities recognised and actively embraced globalisation more than a decade ago, the 1999 "Bologna Process" has now led most European universities and governments to actively promote the internationalisation of the university system. By doing so, they have recognised that a Europe of culture and education, which must develop alongside a Europe of trade, industry and currency – if the European integration process is to succeed –, can only be brought about if future European graduates, as the top performers of European societies, experience the European concept of "unity in diversity" as a significant component of their education, and thus proceed to using this diversity both sensibly and productively as a unique resource. Great productivity

potential lies in the exchange between European cultures, and appropriate structures and forms of co-operation are being developed within the framework of Campus Europae to exploit this potential in a university context.

For more than 1,000 years, Europe has been viewed as having a common culture. Despite the differences in cultural experiences in each individual country, all are linked by a common tradition and an awareness of their "unity in diversity".

With the start of the European university system in the 11th century, it was natural over a period of several hundred years for students and lecturers to move around freely. The "Barbarossa Privilege" afforded the special protection of the King to those migrant scholars who had become "homeless for the love of science (*amore scientiae facti exules*)". Using Latin as the *lingua franca*, universities were international beyond the Age of Enlightenment, without having to emphasise this characteristic.

The era of nationalism, over the past 300 years, has not left the universities unaffected. At times, they became almost strongholds of chauvinistic thought. After the Second World War, however, this nationalist concentration met with little response in European universities. With the end of the Cold War, the last wall which blocked personal mobility and the free exchange of thought has been removed. The path is once again clear for a fresh Europeanisation of the university system.

Internationalisation and globalisation are the dominating phenomena in the current global debate. These phenomena will shape the foreseeable future of science and business, politics and culture, even when confronted with counter-movements seeking to impose regionalism and isolation. The Europeanisation of higher education is therefore not just a key idea in a historical sense. It is, equally, a necessary pre-condition to success in the current endeavours to encourage Europe to grow together politically, culturally and economically, endeavours which will result in a stronger Europe aware of its shared heritage: The foundations for the spiritual unity and strength of Europe lie in the respect for human rights, and in securing scientific universalism.

The restoration of the European dimension in the university system is a necessary prerequisite in order to be able to survive in international competition with American, Asian and Australian universities.

Increased importance is placed upon the personal experiences acquired during a course of study. The systematic integration of inter-cultural activities is not in contrast to, but rather it complements both the “virtual university” of the future, and the Internet’s ever increasing potential for distance learning.

3. Previous experience with the exchange of students and scholars in Europe

Over the past 20 years, the number of programmes supported and financed by the European Union to encourage co-operation in the educational sector, and the number of bilateral activities carried out by individual universities, have had a more or less equal effect in increasing the number of students who have taken advantage of exchange programmes in European or non-European countries. Yet, viewed against the total number of students who have completed their first degree, the figure for exchange students only represents a minority group, and is far below the 10% aim in all disciplines and universities. In the academic year 2001, for instance, the proportion of French, Spanish and German students who participated in the ERASMUS programme to spend between 3 – 12 months studying abroad only represented 1% of all students in each respective country.

More crucial, from a political European point of view, is the fact that this limited movement of students is predominantly focused on only a few member states. For the development of a European identity, an identity which recognises a Europe stretching from the Black Sea to the Atlantic, this limited movement represents an obstacle. The multitude of other countries and languages, whose contributions to the history and development of Europe are significant and indisputable, serve almost the sole function of being “provider countries” within the mobility program. While they encourage “their” students to study abroad, very few students from other countries actually come to them, primarily due to the language barrier. The attempts made in several Eastern European

and Scandinavian countries to encourage young people to study in their countries by offering to hold classes in English or German usually led to a broader and deeper understanding of specific regional and/or European aspects. An in-depth knowledge and understanding of a particular country's culture and specific contribution to European history, and indeed to present-day Europe also, can only be acquired by learning that country's language.

The ERASMUS-programme, on the one hand, and the universities' bilateral partnerships, on the other hand, contribute fairly equally to the mobility of students and lecturers. The universities currently participating in the Campus Europae initiative all have more than 20, and some more than 40, bilateral cooperation agreements with other universities, both European and non-European, and are therefore participants in many international networks. These cooperative agreements also serve to regulate the scope of the exchange of students and teachers. Closer inspection reveals that some of them are of a purely historic value, and do not necessarily apply today. Where partnerships are actively practised, only a low number of student and lecturer exchanges actually take place in some departments or courses of study (two to four people per year).

The participating universities which have made far-reaching agreements, e.g. regarding bilateral final qualifications and university degrees with partner universities, indicate the considerably high level of co-ordination required. The reason for this seems to be due to the problems caused when accrediting the academic results obtained abroad.

Hardly a single European university has more than 2% of its students spending a year at a foreign university. This quota does not however take into consideration how many of these students go to countries where the same language is spoken, such as Germans going to Austria or German-speaking Switzerland, French students going to Belgium, or Britons to the US or Australia.

The multifarious experience which the universities participating in Campus Europae have had with traditional international university co-operation has played an important role in their involvement in the Campus Europae project.

4. Evaluation of previous experience and conclusions

As stated in the Bologna Declaration, the following objectives are considered to be of primary relevance in order to establish the European area of higher education and to promote the European system of higher education world-wide:

1. Adoption of a system of easily readable and comparable degrees.
2. Adoption of a system essentially based on two main cycles, undergraduate and graduate.
3. Establishment of a system of credits – such as in the ECTS system.
4. Promotion of mobility by overcoming obstacles to the effective exercise of free movement.
5. Promotion of European co-operation in quality assurance.
6. Promotion of the necessary European dimensions in higher education.

Campus Europae aims to put these objectives into practice by implementing the following measures – thereby going above and beyond the existing European exchange programmes like ERASMUS and others. These measures take evaluations of such programmes into account.

4.1 Motivation and Recruitment of students

- Situation

The decision to spend a period of study abroad is today almost exclusively a decision made by the individual student. Even for courses which integrate the opportunity to study abroad into their syllabus, e.g. foreign language teacher training, the intensity or duration of study abroad is still very much left to the individual. A selection process is seldom made by the departments since the number of applications usually lies far below the number of available places. The small number of students taking part in exchange programs is therefore not the result of an “elitist strategy” or the “selection of the best”, but rather the consequence of obstacles which continue to exist. Almost all universities report difficulties in motivating students to go abroad for periods of time.

- Conclusions

In accordance with the applicable legal situation, the universities participating in Campus Europae are not allowed to choose their students. With the exception of very few courses of study, universities cannot obligate students to go abroad. However, the project Campus Europae, as well as the idea of a "European Higher Education Area", can only be realised, if the students at the participating universities are motivated to go abroad and qualified to do so successfully.

The following possibilities can help to achieve this:

1. The participating universities characterise their study programs as being offered within the framework of Campus Europae. These programs of study involve clearly defined requirements which must be met. Students should be familiar and in agreement with them before starting their course of study. Students are aware of the fact that they will transfer to a foreign university initially during the BA programme, that means in general after one year of studies. The attractiveness of the study programmes, on the one hand, and the expected level of commitment, on the other hand, determine the students' level of interest and their willingness to excel. In this way, a selection process on the demand side can be expected, without universities themselves having to implement selection measures prior to registration.
2. The participating universities are mutually obliged to support their students during the first year with regard to academic and linguistic qualifications in such a way that they can be expected to successfully continue their course of study at a foreign partner university. Determining a student's suitability for changing over to a partner university is the pre-requisite for the opportunity to continue the course of study at one of the universities participating in Campus Europae.

For universities, this means that the conditions and requirements of study should be sufficiently communicated to interested parties even before the courses have begun. In other words: Student counseling is of the utmost importance. During the first year of study, in addition to providing the relevant academic qualification, universities must also make suitable provisions for achieving the required level of English as well as introducing the student to the "host" language of the country in which the second year abroad will be spent.

Using the experiences of partner universities, the consortium will evaluate the preparatory measures used by participating universities.

4.2 When to study abroad

- Situation

The majority of students today transfer to a foreign university during their third or fourth year of study, and approx. 25% choose to study abroad only after having completed their first degree.

With the current endeavours undertaken in all European countries to strongly regulate BA programmes, since BA degrees are designed to qualify students only for their respective professions, there is the risk that it will not be feasible for students enrolled in such programmes to study abroad for one year. Consequently, studying abroad tends to be a realistic option for MA students only. This, however, contradicts the Bologna intention which is to increase mobility among all European students.

- Conclusions

The universities participating in Campus Europae attach great importance to students being able to spend a year abroad, both as part of their Bachelors and Masters degrees. For three-year BA degrees, this year abroad would take place in the second (i.e. middle) year of study, and for two-year MA degrees, in the first year of study. These, however, are not strict rules. Depending on the degree discipline, it may be more appropriate to take the year abroad at another point in time during the degree. In all cases, it should be ensured that students are able to gain the experience of studying abroad, even during their first degree, upon completion of which they could enter employment.

Despite the fact that the various models of study organization currently used in European countries (see table below) are not all in compliance with the Bologna model, they nevertheless enable these demands to be fulfilled. However, the Campus Europae project aims to speed up the process of adopting the Bologna model ("3 plus 2") in the participating universities.

Example: Present options of going abroad

Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
1 year abroad			1 year abroad	

Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
1 year abroad		1 year abroad	

Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6
1 year abroad				1 year abroad	

This however requires that the course of study be designed in such a way as to allow these periods of study abroad. One must keep in mind that the creation of a “European Higher Education Area” and the convergence of the organisation of study within Europe which was agreed in Bologna are not regulatory measures undertaken by the European education ministers to impede mobility. On the contrary, they are designed to increase mobility.

4.3 Length of stay

- Situation

The average length of stay for a study period abroad under the ERASMUS program is between six and seven months. Given that the framework of this program encourages periods of stay of between three and twelve months, the duration of the majority of stays abroad is considerably less than half an academic year.

The in-depth experience of another culture, which is the aim of the universities participating in the Campus Europae initiative, barely seems feasible during a three-month summer school or one-semester stay.

- Conclusions

Since the aim is not the acquisition of a foreign language, but rather an understanding of how other people think and live, the length of stay should be chosen so that students can become as integrated as possible in the host country. An appropriate length of stay would be twelve months.

Spending an academic year abroad is also a sensible option for organisational reasons. A comparison of the academic calendar shows that all academic years are divided into two sections. However, the start of the various academic years lies between September 1 and October 20, and the duration of the academic half-years (incl. examination period) varies between 14 and 20 weeks. Therefore, "semesters" at individual universities start and end at very different times. The second half-years, then, start between January 15 and April 1. Changing universities at the end of the winter semester or at the start of the second half of the academic year is usually not possible without students losing time.

4.4 Languages

- Situation

Currently, all mobility programs assume that the participants are capable of following classes in the host country's language from the beginning. One exception to this rule is summer schools and similar events, which are frequently taught in English.

The decision that the host country's language should also be the language in which foreign students must complete their course of study has led to a preference for those countries in which a popular language has already been learned at the primary or secondary school level. In Europe, following the demise of the Soviet Union, these languages are, in the main, English and Spanish, and, to a much lesser extent, French, Italian and German.

Today, English is the „interim language“ of the scientific and global communities. Failure to recognise this will lead to isolation and would be counter-productive. It is consequently necessary to have a good command of English – not just for studying abroad, but also for an individual's studies in general. It is appropriate here to draw a parallel with Latin, the

old lingua franca of Europe, or German, which was occasionally used in the same way. So, the „interim language“ of the Campus Europae network should be English.

- Conclusions

This however does not automatically lead to the conclusion that European universities should neglect their national language in favour of English, or even offer classes exclusively in English for foreign students. Europe thrives on the “tonal diversity” of its many tongues and their centuries old mutual relations and cultural diffusion.

Due to the significance of the English language, the universities participating in Campus Europae have decided to use English as an “interim language”. Unless “guest” students are already proficient in the host language, they can take their classes in English for the first half of the academic year to enable them to achieve the required amount of ECTS credits. Classes in English should also form part of the regular curricula for the “home” students in order to facilitate their transition to study abroad. Furthermore, joint classes for home and guest students offer common experience to both groups and foster European integration at “class-level”. Last but not least, it is not economically feasible – at least with certain forms of teaching such as lecturing – to run parallel class offers in both the native language and English. Yet, parallel classes in the local language as well as in English are easy to implement with small-group-classes teaching the same topics: One or more of those classes can be offered in English.

In addition to achieving academic objectives, the Campus Europae initiative will allow students to experience different European countries and cultures. To this end, it is essential to learn the local language as well.

This should take place in the following manner. At the “home university”, students will take relatively short language courses (parallel to their regular course loads, or – alternatively – by way of Internet courses) preparing them for their stay in the country they have chosen. This instruction will be continued in the “host” country before the academic year begins – as is already common in many exchange programs – in the form of an intensive course of up to four weeks. These courses should be continued for at least the first half of the academic year. By combining “organised learning” with the day-to-day experience of using a language in situ, foreign students can achieve a language proficiency which will enable them to

successfully attend classes taught in the local language during the second academic half-year. The question, however, is whether the command of the local language should be at a level to be able to write scientific papers. For this reason, students should have the option to submit written work in English (to be agreed with lecturers).

The objective is that at the end of a five-year course of study, Campus Europae students will be able to express themselves in at least two other European languages in addition to their mother tongue. This combination of using English as an „interim language“ – but predominantly as a language to lower the transition threshold for entering a third language environment – will not lead to the wasting away of “minor” languages, as paradoxical as this may seem initially. Indeed, the opposite is true. It will once again become possible to become acquainted with minority European languages, and appreciate their richness.

The following obstacles currently impede the realisation of this plan:

Firstly, not all lecturers possess the required English language skills to be able to teach in English. Language courses for lecturers could be just as useful here as inviting guest lecturers.

Secondly, there are legal stipulations in many European countries which specify that at least in certain areas of study and exams, the only acceptable language is the local one. However, these legal stipulations are often circumvented for academic reasons and in agreements between lecturers and students. Yet, for certain groups and individuals they represent a politically useful instrument to discourage more communication. It is imperative that participating universities be freed from these legal stipulations.

4.5 Recognition problems

The recognition of higher education qualifications in the European region is laid down in the 1997 Lisbon Convention.

- Situation

The procedure for recognising work undertaken whilst studying abroad is laid down in detail for programs which incorporate bi-national agreements; the courses of study are agreed in detail between the two universities, and the syllabus is, to a great extent, obligatory.

For those participating in the ERASMUS programme, and in exchanges based on partnership agreements between universities, an individual concertation is normally made between the students and the departments. In view of the small number (1-2%) of students who take advantage annually of the offer of participating in an exchange, it is quite possible that issues regarding accreditation can be clarified individually. The development of ECTS in recent years has increasingly simplified the accreditation process.

However, approx. 25% of the students report having difficulties, when returning to their "home university", regarding the accreditation of work undertaken abroad. In light of the fact that these students are a particularly motivated group and that the university departments are involved in the planned exchange at an early stage, i.e. before the period of study abroad commences, this quota is surprisingly high.

Recently, the development of BA curricula in a number of European countries has been showing so much detail regulation, that essential liberality – or broadmindedness – with respect to the transfer of comparable, not identical credits is at risk here.

- Conclusions

The universities participating in the Campus Europae project will make every effort to resolutely apply, uniformly, the ECTS regulatory matters – "one point is one point, be it in Trento or Aveiro". This presupposes basic trust amongst the universities involved. To create such trust and to mutually encourage each other to improve the quality of teaching is – in addition to research cooperation – the essential objective of the lecturer exchange program.

It is not the Campus Europae aim to achieve Europe-wide, joint "multilateral" or harmonised courses of study by agreeing on specific areas of content. Based on the experience of the demanding development of bilateral courses of study and final qualifications, as well as the earlier "equivalence commissions", such an aim is neither possible, nor is it desirable.

Within a system designed to promote mobility, the problem of recognition can best be solved through a combination of stringent ECTS scoring regulations and accompanying “trust building measures”.

This seems possible. Any speculation that the courses of study which lead to particularly “public” occupations, such as teachers or civil servants, and which to a large extent are subject to national regulations, are difficult to co-ordinate in a multinational context, is only partly justified.

Even today, students studying to be teachers of modern languages, are required to spend a part of their course of study in the country where this language is spoken. Students preparing to teach mathematics and natural sciences, also, can easily spend part of their course of study abroad, since these disciplines are already “international”. In order to raise the quality of teaching in some European countries, results of comparative international school performance tests (TIMMS, PISA, etc.) indicate that it is desirable to gain experience in the fields of educational science and actual classroom teaching. However, in some countries there is only a limited offer of available disciplines such as educational science and didactics, or the courses available contain only very few elements specific to teacher training. However, the importance of teacher training to the whole project requires that pressure for a successful outcome regarding this subject area is particularly important.

As European integration and globalisation progresses, the European and international aspects of legal, administrative and economic science are becoming more important, which is why particular importance is being attached here to achieving a quantitative expansion of the “European dimension”. This should not occur solely or primarily in such a way as to increase the presence in the curriculum of European material – in the narrow sense – such as European law, comparative law and legal co-ordination. It should occur mainly in such a way as to emphasise the common European legal way of thinking by understanding the system and the methodology of law (incorporating English law as a contrasting element). The co-operation between universities is specially suited to finding such opportunities which can be regulated or implemented by the universities themselves – if possible without the intervention of ministerial authorities and parliaments. The Bachelors and Masters structures are very suitable in this respect.

In view of the diversity of subject-specific peculiarities, any attempt to find a solution at a professional level for the problem of accrediting work undertaken whilst studying abroad seems futile. Here, ECTS offers a suitable approach. The universities participating in the Campus Europae initiative have therefore agreed on the following procedure:

- a. Students must be able to achieve 60 ECTS points in each of the academic years at the host universities. This is a prerequisite for being awarded the Campus Europae degree (120 ECTS points from foreign universities where different languages are spoken).
- b. In each subject, such an offer should constitute 30 ECTS points (if possible with additional 15 ECTS points as electives) in English, and 30 ECTS points in the local language (again, plus 15 ECTS points as electives).
- c. Classes taught in English, as the interim language, are limited and represent an additional drain on the universities' resources. Therefore, these courses should be chosen in such a way that they can be accredited by as many universities as possible.
- d. Each subject area in the participating universities informs the counterpart in the other universities about which courses they wish to offer for this purpose, paying particular attention to select subjects with excellent academic profiles.
- e. The subject areas at the other participating universities should check which of the courses offered are compatible with the local study programme, and which can therefore be easily accredited. Since these checks are only to be carried out (step by step) for courses of study in a subject area, the local effort is justifiable even if queries and amendments are necessary to achieve a 90 ECTS point offer (see b.).
- f. At the end of this process, all of the participating universities can advise students at which university they can undertake which courses of study.

Within the framework of Campus Europae, representatives of the participating universities have formed subject committees comprising the fields of business administration and economics, engineering, humanities and social sciences, law, medicine, natural sciences and teacher training. These committees have checked the stipulations listed in points a. to f. from a subject-specific perspective, and they have found them practicable after different implementation periods.

There are, however, two major obstacles:

Firstly, there is an obvious tendency in many European countries to regulate BA programmes to such a degree – or organise them in such a way – that it seems imperative for students to stay “at home”. Studying abroad becomes impossible without loosing time.

Secondly, certain phases of study are followed by competitions. In order to take part in these competitions successfully, students need to stay “at home” for the complete study phase.

As a consequence, study periods abroad are realistic only upon completion of the respective study phases (BA or MA). This would prevent those students from going abroad, who begin their professional careers after the first study phase (BA).

By standardising the accreditation procedure, and not the course syllabi, the regulations suggested here serve to make the procedures more manageable and transparent for students and universities, involving minimal effort and resources. They do not impede other forms and ways of student transfer. There is of course the possibility that after one year abroad, students might decide not to go “home”, but instead choose to stay a further year and complete their BA at the foreign university. If this occurs frequently, a procedure can be developed, which also incorporates the first year of study into a multilateral accreditation process. As the “home university” and therefore the place where tuition fees are to be paid is to be changed, this will have repercussions regarding the payment of tuition fees, as detailed in the following section.

Naturally, the course of study can be continued at a university in a non-European country, or at one which is not part of the Campus Europae project.

4.6 Tuition fees

- *Situation*

Within the framework of partnership agreements and the ERASMUS program, the regulations regarding tuition fees state that students at the “host university” are exempt from paying tuition fees. They continue to be classified as students at their “home university”, who have been “delegated” to study abroad.

These regulations imply that the normal tuition fees should continue to be paid. Some universities and countries however expressly waive tuition fees for “their” students, thus supporting a period of study abroad. At the same time, the universities are obliged within the framework of the exchange programmes, to refrain from levying tuition fees on visiting students. Due to the small number of exchange students within the framework of partnership and ERASMUS programs, this waiver of tuition fees is of little importance to university and national budgets.

- *Conclusions*

With the increase in the number of exchange students under the Campus Europae system, the issue of tuition fees takes on a significant financial dimension. Within the framework of Campus Europae, the number of students changing universities should be approximately 40% per year and not only 1-2% . Participating universities should be obliged to take countermeasures against a concentration of applications to study at a small number of universities. These include appropriate advice and support, as well as attractive offers (“service packages”). A suitable control process is needed, particularly since admission quotas are limited.

There are three different approaches regarding tuition fees:

1. The voucher model: each student is allocated a sum which corresponds to the average study costs at his/her home university. This sum goes to the host university, which then charges the delegating university or country for the respective amounts. In the current system, universities do not receive their resources as a per capita grant based on their total enrollment. They are allocated personnel and assets based on an assumed capacity figure.

This model is not realistic unless there is a fundamental change in the way in which universities are financed.

2. Tuition fees are paid at the host university. This would ensure that all students studying at the same institution are treated equally. What would however be a disadvantage is that the costs of studying are harder to forecast at the beginning of a course of study. Additionally, national promotional schemes – e.g. the waiving of home university tuition fees when studying abroad – would become ineffective.
3. Tuition fees continue to be paid to the home university, even whilst studying abroad. This model has the advantage that the costs of studying can be calculated from the outset. In light of a fundamentally risk-laden long-term decision, the ability to calculate the financial implications of this decision is an important safety aspect. Moreover, this ensures that national promotional measures can benefit the desired target groups (social exemption from tuition fees, promotion of certain subject disciplines and courses of study etc.).

Having considered all aspects pertaining to this issue, the participating universities have in principle decided on the second approach. However, the third approach might be chosen by the participants as an “interim solution”, due to its being the “normal” tuition procedure at present. The implications of this “interim solution” for individual participating universities would need to be evaluated before a final decision is taken.

4.7 Accommodation

- Situation

Providing assistance in finding or allocating accommodation is an important yet difficult task for the host university. Within the ERASMUS programme, 60-70% of the students report that they were provided with accommodation by the host university. In view of the small numbers of exchange students under ERASMUS, this is possible. Yet, universities are already warning that, before student mobility can increase, serious attempts must be made to provide additional accommodation for exchange students.

Reports of difficulty in accommodating ERASMUS students are especially common in large European cities.

- Conclusions

Providing accommodation will be a major problem for the universities participating in Campus Europae, since a 20-fold increase in student demand can be expected in comparison with previous exchange programmes. Even if not all students immediately take up the Campus Europae offer, the significant increase in demand will have a drastic effect on local housing markets, both with regard to the selection of accommodation in general and prices of accommodation in particular.

The importance of obtaining accommodation is also emphasised by the fact that living expenses, and therefore the cost of the entire period spent abroad, are essentially determined by the cost of the accommodation.

Accommodation assistance by the host university is not just about the provision of accommodation itself. Repeatedly in the past, universities have rented private residential blocks for use as dormitories for all foreign students. Such "home solutions" contradict the idea of Campus Europae.

A large part of the demand for accommodation can be satisfied by having incoming students take over outgoing students' rooms. However, there are numerous universities where students live with their parents. Making use of this accommodation would in most cases be a serious imposition on foreign students and their families.

Participating universities should therefore be responsible for an "organised" market, i.e. a market which is regulated in terms of price and quality. The objective must be to offer accommodation to those foreign students who have no opportunity of finding it themselves whilst they are still at their home university, and to enable them to move into specific accommodation within a week of their arrival.

4.8 Living costs / Support

- Situation

For approximately 60% of ERASMUS students, studying abroad represents an additional financial burden. The additional funds needed average between €150 - €200 per month. This amount however cannot be considered the norm. The difference in living costs for students in each European country is considerable. It therefore seems reasonable to suggest that the support provided should depend on the place of study. Even if such a tiered system of support is possible within the ERASMUS programme, an identical foreign supplement amounting to roughly half of what students state as their additional expenses is normally paid.

A number of European countries support their students' study abroad through additional grants or by exempting them from tuition fees at the home university.

In addition to the difference in costs at the final destination, the form of funding at the home university can have a considerable influence on whether or not studying abroad can become a financial burden. An increasing number of students subsidize at least a part of their living costs through part-time employment, usually in the students' home town.

- Conclusions

For each university location, the average cost of living for students not living with their parents must be ascertained.

Campus Europae's support system should be able to cover higher living costs for socially disadvantaged students.

Furthermore, specific attempts should be made to give foreign students the chance to work during their stay abroad. Firstly, this is obviously useful for financial reasons. Secondly, and just as important, by integrating students into the regional employment market, they will considerably increase their linguistic capabilities and become more familiar with the country's employment culture, thereby improving their perspectives as future graduates.

The Campus Europae initiative must therefore promote its model among employer organisations and trade unions, not only to make the attractiveness of such qualified academics for the European labour market clear, but also to give students the opportunity to acquire experience by working abroad.

4.9 Exchange of Faculty

- Situation

Within the framework of partnership agreements and the ERASMUS program, lecturer exchanges normally are between one week and two months. Longer stays would have to take into consideration the possibility of either the entire family participating in the exchange or considerable travel expenses. Guest professorships are not realistic alternatives, since these usually result in considerable financial losses for the staff involved.

The linguistic competence of lecturers, in particular their ability to teach in English, is not equally available in all subject areas.

- Conclusions

Campus Europae will allow the following targets to be achieved more easily:

- trouble-free mutual recognition of studies abroad
- learning from each other will lead to a qualitative improvement in teaching
- setting up joint teaching and research projects
- development of joint final examinations

These can only be achieved if teachers know both their colleagues and the teaching and research requirements at the other participating universities, and can become familiar with their the learning and working cultures. This includes chairing seminars, advising students, involvement with examinations and contribution to the organisation of student projects. The length of stay should therefore be long enough to complete a constructive lecture period at the host university, i.e. half an academic year (semester), plus an examination period.

Specific efforts are required to motivate lecturers to spend longer periods of time at other universities. From a financial perspective, this can be best supported by the exchange of lecturers in the guise of "service at another location". This means that lecturers sent to other universities will teach there under the same obligations as at their home university and continue to be paid their home salary.

The guest lecturer's teaching hours should correspond with those normally required at the host university. However, to maintain an incentive for participating in the scheme, the number of teaching hours at the host university should not exceed those at the home university. At first, the number of compulsory teaching hours could be reduced, provided this is due to the reorganisation (language, research organisation, administration-related additional burdens) or can be justified by synchronising with the employees at the host university.

Regarding the increased financial cost (travel expenses, accommodation, food, etc.), the terms of the respective national agencies responsible for supporting the employment of academics abroad are applicable.

A pre-requisite for taking part in such an exchange is that lecturers be proficient in English. Provisions to specifically promote linguistic competence are just as necessary as the (initial) bonus given to those lecturers who teach in English, be it in the form of a financial incentive or a reduction of the minimum number of compulsory hours.

4.10 Campus Europae and its contribution to the development of European Universities

Campus Europae takes up the suggestions made in Bologna, Salamanca and Prague, and aims to implement them quickly within the "European Higher Education Area" by taking the experiences of previous exchange programmes into account and giving them new impulses:

1. The Campus Europae project adds a European dimension to higher education by providing students with an in-depth knowledge of at least three different European regions (during BA/MA-programmes – "3 plus 2").

2. The project will enable students to experience the “European Higher Education Area” initially during BA-programmes – i.e. during the first study phase. This will ensure that those students who will enter professional life – temporarily or permanently – upon graduating with a BA degree can also acquire “European competence”.
3. The Campus Europae project demonstrates the European idea of “unity in diversity” by bringing students in contact with the so-called “minor” European countries and languages.
4. The Campus Europae study programme will enable students graduating with a BA degree to communicate in at least three European languages (two for English native speakers). Students graduating with an MA degree should be able to communicate in at least four (respectively three) European languages.
5. Using a new concept of academic exchange, Campus Europae encourages participating universities to improve the quality of their teaching and the transparency of their courses.
6. Campus Europae increases the international competitiveness and attractiveness of the participating universities.
7. Campus Europae will show the possibility of diversification within study programmes and their mutual recognition without implementing rigid standardization measures.
8. The large number of foreign students will lead to internationalisation: changes in lifestyle and learning culture at the respective universities.
9. Campus Europae adds a European dimension to university degrees and improves employment prospects for graduates in Europe and world wide.

Campus Europae accepts the legal structures presently existing in relation to its participant universities. Therefore, participation is open to any European university, and there are no barriers to entry other than acceptance of the Charter of the European University Foundation.

What is new is inter-university co-operation on four fronts:

- a. the emphasis on the European idea and the objective of promoting a European identity,
- b. the promotion of an early period of study abroad,
- c. the way it addresses linguistic issues,
- d. the use of a standardised procedure for the accreditation of studies.

Particularly, the new approach to linguistic issues (see c. above) will give smaller European countries the chance to attract students from other EU countries.

There are no evident reasons why the Campus Europae concept cannot be applied to other universities or university consortiums not already included under its aegis. The provisions of Campus Europae serve to use Europe's cultural diversity as a competitive advantage and to prepare European students for a future in the global marketplace and within multicultural environments.

[...]

7 Outlook

One main Campus Europae endeavour seeks to build a network of co-operating universities. Currently, the most concrete and advanced efforts in implementing the "Bologna Process" are placed forth, thereby strengthening Europe's role in culture, academia, technology, and economics.

The participating universities embark on the Campus Europae process with an entrepreneurial, open, and co-operative spirit. Each university will offer students a first rate education grounded in the European tradition of diversity and academic excellency.

This document demonstrates the progress already made through the efforts of presidents, rectors, deans and individual faculty members. Their work defines Campus Europae's objectives and offers solutions to multiple large and small operational challenges arising from the program's intricate network system. Such efforts strongly indicate that remaining

tasks will be tackled with the same spirit of co-operation and entrepreneurship. So, participating universities are convinced that at the end of the planning phase, the Campus Europae process can be implemented at the beginning of the 2004 academic year.

To effectively achieve such a goal, the participating universities and the co-ordinating initiative, under the Grand Duchy's leadership, will immediately seek support for the Campus Europae concept from the Commission of the European Union and the European Parliament. National governments and parliaments will also be approached for support. The Campus Europae team will additionally obtain support from European and national organisations representing institutions of higher education. The European University Foundation will be established in due course as a co-ordinating mechanism and as a permanent forum of exchange.

Campus Europae is an open network inviting participation from all European universities sharing its basic philosophy. Membership into Campus Europae provides each university's students and faculty with an experience into Europe's diverse academic life. Campus Europae will enhance each university by offering every participating institution global and intellectual competitiveness. Campus Europae is also a learning network. All organisations are confronted with significant environments changes, and academic institutions are no exceptions. Participating universities are convinced, that despite efforts made in the planning process, a need will arise to carefully evaluate the experience already gained, especially the experience acquired from the first years of implementation. So, changes, improvements, and adaptations to newly emerging opportunities will be a consistent and vital element to the Campus Europae network. The principle Campus Europae process, "diversity and unity", should enable participating universities to wrestle with developing risks and opportunities in the same entrepreneurial and co-operative spirit with which they embarked on the Campus Europae process two years ago.

Signed by:

**Centre Universitaire de Luxembourg
European Humanities University, Minsk, Belarus**

Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain
University Henri Poincaré (Nancy I), France
University of Aveiro, Portugal
University of Greifswald, Germany
University of Hamburg, Germany
University of Liège, Belgium
University of Limerick, Ireland
University of Latvia, Latvia
University of Trento, Italy
University of Vienna, Austria